

Vector backbone: pBluescript KS
 PmH4p, *P. multistriata* H4 gene promoter; GFP, green fluorescent protein; MRM2, Mating-type Related Minus 2 gene coding sequence; Gene ID: 0006960 (Russo et al., 2018); PtLhcf1t, *P. tricornutum* Lhcf1 gene terminator.
 This plasmid is suitable for *P. multistriata* biolistic transformation and is used to overexpress and tag the MRM2 gene.